

Beam-focusing in near-field communications: enhancing the physical layer security

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Abstract—Recent theoretical work proposes incorporating near-field engineering in future wireless communications, to generate focused beams that are able to address the challenges of high frequencies more efficiently than conventional beam-forming. Previously we derived an exact analytical model for beam-focusing at oblique angles, based on explicit electromagnetic modeling. Our model is a powerful tool for analyzing the physical layer security capabilities of such beams, as it provides analytical description of the spatial distribution of the focused power. In this work we study analytically the enhancement of the physical layer security offered by such beams, and we demonstrate their superiority with respect to beams generated with conventional beam-forming. We analyze the dependencies between the beam’s characteristics and the location of a possible eavesdropper, and we introduce metrics to assess secure and vulnerable areas.

I. INTRODUCTION

As wireless communications are nowadays shifting to higher frequencies, the availability of electrically large surfaces, such as large antenna arrays (LAAs) and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs), opens up new opportunities for manipulating the wavefront of generated beams, to acquire curvature beyond the typical far-field planar form, achieved with conventional beam-forming, and focus the power at selected areas [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6].

A direct consequence of beam-focusing is that large gain can be concentrated in a small area, to increase the received power at the user and suppress the transmitted power at nearby regions. Such a possibility promises to enhance the physical layer security (PLS), as the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of a potential eavesdropper that attempts to tap the communication link can be severely degraded. Recent works on PLS have studied the secrecy capacity of multiple-input, multiple-output (MIMO) systems [7], [8] within the plane wave approximation, providing closed-form expressions for the ergodic secrecy capacity [9], as well as techniques to improve the MIMO performance, including artificial noise [10], deep learning [11] and power allocation [12]. The possibility to increase PLS with near-field beam-forming was studied in [13], [14] for downlink transmissions, in [15] for uplink communications, and in [16] for both uplink and downlink, also demonstrating the increase in the jamming rejection.

Previously [6] we derived an exact analytical model for

beam-focusing at oblique angles, based on explicit electromagnetic modeling. Our model predicts the spatial distribution of the focused beam and the power delivered to the user at any location, for beams generated with large apertures, such as LAAs and RISs, and is therefore a powerful tool to analyze the PLS capabilities of beam-focusing. In this work we study analytically the enhancement of the physical layer security offered by such beams, and we demonstrate their superiority with respect to beams generated with conventional beam-forming. We analyze the dependencies between the beam’s characteristics and the location of a possible eavesdropper, and we introduce metrics to assess secure and vulnerable areas.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Let us consider a large aperture, such as a LAA or a RIS, located at the origin of the coordinate system, with its surface extending on the xy -plane. The aperture generates beams that propagate on the xz -plane, as shown in Fig. 1 and the location of the user equipment (UE) is characterized by the angle θ_{UE} and the distance d_{UE} from the aperture. For typical beam-forming, the footprint of the beam at the aperture usually extends over a few wavelengths, with a flat wavefront that is tilted to direct the beam towards the angle θ_r (steering angle), as shown in Fig. 1(a). To maximize the received power, the aperture steers the beam towards the UE, i.e. $\theta_r = \theta_{\text{UE}}$. For beam-focusing, the footprint of the beam is usually several wavelengths wide [6] with a spherical (or parabolic) wavefront tilted towards the desired direction θ_r . The wavefront curvature is characterized by the parameter f_0 , the focal distance. To maximize the power at the UE, the beam is directed towards the UE, i.e. $\theta_r = \theta_{\text{UE}}$ and is focused on the UE, i.e. $f_0 = d_{\text{UE}}$, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

Following the analysis in [6], the footprint of the beam at the aperture is modeled by a y -polarized Gaussian distribution

$$\mathbf{E}(x, y) = E_0 \exp\left(-\frac{(x \cos \theta_i)^2 + y^2}{w_0^2}\right) \exp(-jk \sin \theta_i x) \hat{\mathbf{y}}, \quad (1)$$

where E_0 is a complex constant, w_0 the radius of the footprint at normal incidence ($\theta_i = 0$), $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the free-space wavenumber and λ the wavelength. This model takes into account possible initial wavefront tilt, e.g. when the beam

Fig. 1. System model of a communication link, mediated by (a) beam-forming and (b) beam-focusing. The beam is directed towards the UE to maximize the received power, i.e. $\theta_r = \theta_{UE}$, $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$ for beam-forming and $\theta_r = \theta_{UE}$, $f_0 = d_{UE}$ for beam-focusing. (c) Schematic illustration of the link, with the blue point marking the UE location and the red disk (also shown in the bottom-left inset) denoting the possible locations of the eavesdropper. The insets on the right depict cross-sections of both beams along the LoS (top panel) and perpendicular to the LoS (bottom panel).

is generated with a RIS and the incident beam impinges at oblique incidence ($\theta_i \neq 0$). In this case the footprint acquires elliptical shape, with the major axis of the ellipse residing on the x -axis [17]. The choice $E_0 = \sqrt{4Z_0 P_t \cos \theta_i} / \pi w_0^2$ ensures that $\iint |S_r|^2 = P_t$, where P_t is the total power (Watts) of the beam.

Using the footprint in (1), the power density at any observation point on the xz -plane is given by [6]

$$S_r(x, z) = \frac{2P_t \cos \theta_i}{\pi w_0^2} |R|^2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z}{z_R \cos \theta_r}\right)^2}} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z}{z_R \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{\cos \theta_r}\right)^4}} \times \exp\left[-\frac{2(x \cos \theta_r - z \sin \theta_r)^2}{w_0^2 \left(\left(\frac{\cos \theta_r}{\cos \theta_i} - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z \cos \theta_i}{z_R \cos^2 \theta_r}\right)^2\right)}\right], \quad (2)$$

where Z_0 is the free-space wave impedance and $z_R = \pi w_0^2 / \lambda$ is the Rayleigh length. Note that, for $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$, (2) yields the received power for conventional beam-forming [18], [19]. The parameter R accounts for possible losses ($|R| \leq 1$), e.g.

reflection losses when the beam is generated by a RIS.

The eavesdropper, which we will refer to as *eve*, is located in the vicinity of the UE, attempting to tap the communication link between the legitimate user (UE) and the aperture. It can be found anywhere within an ellipse with axes D_x, D_y , as illustrated in the bottom-left inset of Fig. 1(c). Along the aperture-UE line-of-sight (LoS) beams generated with beam-forming decay as $\propto 1/r^2$, while focused beams are maximized at the UE (see top-right inset). Therefore, the power received by the eve can be substantially reduced with beam-focusing. At the UE location, perpendicular to the LoS, focused beams decay sharply (see bottom-right inset), indicating that signals at the side of the beam can be significantly suppressed.

III. POWER RATIO BETWEEN EAVESDROPPER AND USER

Focusing offers the capability of concentrating the transmitted power at small areas and, hence, increasing the power at the user, without the need to increase the power at the transmitter. Therefore, it is instructive to first study the power ratio between the user, where the power is maximized, and the eve, which resides in the vicinity. In our examples the aperture always directs the beam towards the UE, i.e. $\theta_r = \theta_{UE}$. For beam-forming $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$ and for beam-focusing the beam is focused at the UE, i.e. $f_0 = d_{UE}$.

Let us consider a D-band indoor scenario with operation frequency of 150 GHz. Without loss of generality we consider $\theta_i = 0^\circ$, $R = 1$, and for beam-forming we use a narrow footprint of $w_0 = 1$ cm, while for beam-focusing we use a wide footprint of $w_0 = 40$ cm. The UE is located at $\theta_{UE} = 30^\circ$, $d_{UE} = 8$ m and is illuminated by the aperture with conventional beam-forming and with beam-focusing, receiving power P_{UE} ; the eve, located within the elliptical disk centered at the UE, receives power P_{eve} . To calculate the cumulative density function (CDF) of the power ratio P_{eve}/P_{UE} , $F(P_{eve}/P_{UE})$, we take 10^5 random locations of the eve, uniformly distributed across the disk surface.

The beam profiles analyzed in Fig. 1(c) indicate that, for a focused beam, there are two limiting cases with respect to the range of the power ratio; it is maximized along the LoS (worst case scenario for PLS) and it is minimized along the direction perpendicular to the LoS at the UE position (best case scenario for PLS). Therefore, we start with these two limiting cases. In the notation of the ellipse axes, the former case corresponds to $D_x = 0$, $D_y \equiv D$ and the latter case to $D_x \equiv D$, $D_y = 0$, as illustrated in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b), respectively.

For an eve located along the LoS, the power ratio can be relatively large for beam-forming, as shown in Fig. 2(c), and even exceed unity. This is not unexpected, because the beam power density decays as $\propto 1/r^2$ along its propagation path and, hence, eves that are located between the aperture and the UE may receive power that is larger than what reaches the UE. This becomes more pronounced as D increases, essentially including more locations between the aperture and the UE. With beam-focusing the performance is significantly improved, as shown in Fig. 2(e). Increasing D has the effect of spreading the eve position at more locations far from the

Fig. 2. CDF of power ratio P_{eve}/P_{UE} in the vicinity of the UE, as a function of the path length D , on which the eve is located. (a),(c),(e) Eve position along the LoS. (b) Eve position perpendicular to the LoS. The UE location is characterized by $\theta_{UE} = 30^\circ$ and $d_{UE} = 8$ m.

UE where the beam peak is located, and therefore reducing the power ratio. This behavior is also met in beam-forming, for eve located along the line perpendicular to the LoS. In this case the beam has its peak at the UE and, with increasing D , the power ratio is reduced, as shown in Fig. 2(d). What is impressive, though, is the dramatic effect of beam-focusing, as a result of the narrow focal spot. As shown in Fig. 2(f), the power ratio is restricted mainly to very low values, practically regardless of the path length D .

In Fig. 3 we study the same configuration in a more general case where the eve is located on a circular disk of diameter D . The CDFs result from several eve locations within the two limiting cases of Fig. 2 and are, in essence, averaged to yield intermediate results. Due to the elongated shape of the beams, the probability of the eve's location to be at low power areas is higher, and, hence the results are closer to those previously obtained for $D_y = 0$.

In Fig. 4 we study the impact of the focused beam parameters on the power ratio P_{eve}/P_{UE} . For different UE positions we calculate the CDF of the power ratio, using the worst case scenario of Fig. 3 for the eve, i.e. a circular disk with the smallest diameter $D = 1$ m. In each case the beam follows the UE, and focuses the power at the UE

Fig. 3. CDF of power ratio P_{eve}/P_{UE} in the vicinity of the UE, as a function of the disk diameter D , in which the eve is located. (a) Beam-forming, and (b) beam-focusing, for a UE location characterized by $\theta_{UE} = 30^\circ$ and $d_{UE} = 8$ m.

location. In Fig. 4(a) we calculate the CDF for various focal distances along the direction $\theta_r = 30^\circ$, and in Fig. 4(c) we repeat the calculations for various steering angles θ_r and fixed focal distance $f_0 = 8$ m. We observe that the probability to achieve a certain power ratio below some threshold reduces with increasing steering angle and/or focal distance. This means that the probability for the power ratio to be above the same threshold increases, which is not unexpected; the power density at the focal distance can be calculated using (2) with $x = f_0 \sin \theta_r$, $z = f_0 \cos \theta_r$, which leads to

$$S_{r,\text{focal}} = 2\pi \frac{P_t |R|^2 w_0^2 \cos^2 \theta_r}{\lambda^2 f_0^2 \cos^2 \theta_i}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4. CDF of power ratio P_{eve}/P_{UE} , as a function of the focused beam properties, for eve located within a disk of diameter $D = 1$ m. (a),(b) Beam focused along the linear trajectory characterized by $\theta_r = 30^\circ$. (c),(d) Beam focused at $f_0 = 8$ m, along a circular trajectory.

Fig. 5. Average secrecy rate $\langle S \rangle$ (bps/Hz) at each UE location within the designated area, for eve located within a disk of diameter $D = 1$ m, centered at the UE. (a),(c) Beam-forming ($w_0 = 1$ cm) and (b),(d) beam-focusing ($w_0 = 40$ cm). (a),(b) $SNR_{UE} = 10$ dB, and (c),(d) $SNR_{UE} = 20$ dB. The colormaps have been saturated to emphasize the details in each case.

The form of (3) dictates that, for constant incident power P_t , $S_{r,focal}$ decreases with larger focal distance and/or steering angle. As a result, the contrast between the power at the focal area and its vicinity reduces, therefore increasing the power ratio. The same occurs with reduced footprint size, as also verified here in the examples of Fig. 4(b),(d), where we use a footprint of smaller radius $w_0 = 20$ cm.

IV. SECRECY RATE AND SECURITY MAPS

The power ratio is a useful metric for assessing the beam-focusing PLS performance, however does not take the noise power into account. This is crucial, because a certain power ratio that in the absence of noise would allow for wiretapping, in the presence of noise could suppress or entirely eliminate such a possibility. Therefore, for practical situations, it is more relevant to consider a measure based on the channel capacity that takes into account the SNR. PLS is usually assessed by the secrecy rate, which is the difference between the capacity of the legitimate user and the eavesdropper [20], i.e.

$$S = \log_2(1 + SNR_{UE}) - \log_2(1 + SNR_{eve}), \quad (4)$$

where $SNR_{eve} = P_{eve}/P_N$ is the SNR at the eve, $SNR_{UE} = P_{UE}/P_N$ is the SNR at the UE, and P_N is the noise power. To understand the impact of noise in the calculated secrecy

Fig. 6. Maps of secure (green) and vulnerable (red) areas. The maps depict the probability of $S > S_{th}$ at each UE location within the designated area. Examples for $D = 1$ m and $S_{th} = 3$ bps/Hz. (a),(b) $SNR_{UE} = 10$ dB, and (c),(d) $SNR_{UE} = 20$ dB. The footprint radius is (a),(c) $w_0 = 20$ cm, and (b),(d) $w_0 = 40$ cm. The white regions mark the probability of 0.95.

rate we write (4) in terms of the power ratio and the SNR at the UE, as

$$S = \log_2 \left(\frac{1 + SNR_{UE}^{-1}}{\frac{SNR_{eve}}{SNR_{UE}} + SNR_{UE}^{-1}} \right). \quad (5)$$

For $SNR_{eve}/SNR_{UE} \rightarrow 0$ we see that $S \rightarrow \log_2(1 + SNR_{UE})$, i.e. S is maximized, and for $SNR_{UE} \rightarrow \infty$, we see that $S \rightarrow -\log_2 SNR_{eve}/SNR_{UE}$, which increases with reduced power ratio; therefore, the higher the SNR at the UE and the lower the power ratio, the higher the secrecy rate can be.

While these observations are straightforward for a fixed eve-UE topology, the assessment of UE locations with high or low S becomes more complicated when the eve can be located anywhere within a certain region around the UE. One approach to assess the vulnerability of certain UE locations to wiretapping is by calculating $\langle S \rangle$, the average secrecy rate, for all possible eve locations in the vicinity of the UE. In Fig. 5 we map $\langle S \rangle$ for both beam-forming and beam-focusing, for all possible locations of the UE within the designated area; note that, for each UE location, the beam follows the UE and so does the eve, which resides in a disk of diameter $D = 1$ m centered at the UE. For beam-forming, $\langle S \rangle$ acquires its maximum at the aperture, and quickly diminishes at farther UE locations, contrary to beam-focusing, where $\langle S \rangle$ remains practically constant across the entire area. In the case of beam-forming $\langle S \rangle$ acquires even negative values, which is no surprise; as shown in the inset of Fig. 1(c), for eves located between the aperture and the UE it is possible that $P_{eve} > P_{UE}$, leading

to higher capacity at the eave and, consequently, negative S . In the case of beam-focusing $\langle S \rangle$ is always non-negative, since the beam power is maximized always at the UE. Increasing the SNR at the UE has little effect in case of beam-forming, due to the high power ratio for the majority of the UE locations, which saturates S according to (5). On the contrary, for beam-focusing, the power ratio remains low practically everywhere, leading to improved performance across the entire area when the SNR increases.

We can now turn to the previous examples and ask what is the probability that S is above a certain threshold S_{th} , within the disk of all possible eave locations. As the UE moves within the indoor environment, the beam follows the UE and we can calculate the probability of $S > S_{\text{th}}$ at all UE locations, subsequently mapping secure and vulnerable areas for the UE. In Fig. 6 we present such security maps, where the secure areas are denoted with green and the vulnerable areas with red. The white zone marks the boundary between the two, which in our example corresponds to a probability of 0.95 for $S_{\text{th}} = 3$ bps/Hz. The eave follows the UE at each location, within a disk of $D = 1$ m diameter and the SNR ranges from 10 dB to 20 dB. In Fig. 6(a),(c) we use a beam with $w_0 = 20$ cm footprint. The calculations reveal that the area in front of the aperture is the safest, and expands with increasing SNR, as S overall increases. When the footprint radius is increased to $w_0 = 40$ cm [see Fig. 6(b),(d)] focused beams are formed with increased efficiency [6], in turn expanding further the safe area.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work we studied the enhancement of the physical layer security offered by focused beams, using our analytically derived model for beam-focusing, which is based on explicit electromagnetic modeling. We demonstrated their superiority with respect to beams generated with conventional beam-forming, we analyzed the dependencies between the beam's characteristics and the possible locations of eavesdroppers, and we introduced metrics to assess secure and vulnerable areas.

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